

Our Energy's

OER (Open Educational Resources) Policy

(draft OER policy design for the H2020 project NEWCOMERS and its Our Energy platform)

Study programme: Master in Leadership in Open Education, University of Nova Gorica

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1. Introduction

1.1 Basic information about the NEWCOMERS project and the Our Energy platform

The basis for this OER policy design assignment is the current stage of development of the Horizon 2020 NEWCOMERS project (NEWCOMERS = **New clean energy communities** in a changing European energy system – www.newcomersH2020.eu) and its key communication and dissemination deliverable: the Our Energy online platform for education and awareness-raising (www.our-energy.eu). The author of this assignment is the leader of the Work Package (WP) focussed on the project's communication, dissemination and exploitation activities.

EU energy policy background: the role of the »NEWCOMERS«

The European Union puts **citizens at the core of clean energy transitions**. Beyond policy, disruptive innovations in energy sectors are challenging the traditional business model of large energy utilities. One such disruptive, social innovation is the **emergence of new clean energy communities** (“NEWCOMERS”).

The possible benefits of these communities for their members and the society at large are still emerging and their potential to support the goals of the Energy Union is unclear. By taking an interdisciplinary approach and through employing co-creation strategies, in which participants are actively involved in the design and implementation of the research, the NEWCOMERS project delivers **practical recommendations on how the European Union, as well as national and local governments, can support new clean energy communities** to help them flourish and unfold their potential benefits for citizens and the Energy Union.

Education, awareness-raising and networking inside and between these energy communities and with the key energy-sector stakeholders are highly important for the successful operations of energy communities. They are the central research focus of the NEWCOMERS project, and the Our Energy online platform (www.our-energy.eu) was developed and launched in November 2020 to serve this purpose.

Designing a policy for the “Our Energy” online platform

The online platform has already been launched and is quite comprehensive, but it is lacking a policy that fully articulates its purpose and the activities it must achieve to reach its goal.

Our Energy is an online platform for education, awareness-raising and networking, focusing on energy communities, energy transitions and related topics. It offers short, interactive multimedia content about the current and future role of new clean energy communities, touching on social, economic, business, regulatory, policy, technological, environmental and other aspects.

It is intended for energy communities, their members, and other interested citizens, as well as policymakers and decision-makers, energy-sector corporate actors, researchers, and other key stakeholders involved in the achievement of low-carbon energy transitions. The platform offers up-

to-date and expert-reviewed facts, knowledge, advice and inspiration about energy and energy communities in the form of short (10 to 15 minutes), interactive, advanced multimedia presentations. Content is regularly updated.

Free access and open educational resources. All educational and awareness-raising content is freely accessible without registration. Selected parts of the multimedia presentations are offered as OER that are ready for reuse, remix and other forms of adaptation tailored to the user's educational, community, business or other needs. The openness of Our Energy's resources is planned to be further improved in 2021 as the platform was not initially planned with the criteria of openness.

A collaborative co-learning space. The Our Energy platform disseminates findings of the NEWCOMERS project as well as of many other research projects and organisations, evolving into a collaborative open space for strengthening energy literacy in energy communities.

1.2 Two-step project purpose and the Open Science aspect of Our Energy's future development

The purpose of this assignment is defined in two steps:

- First, the **short-term purpose**: to discuss the key OER policy design aspects of the existing Our Energy platform;
- Second, the **long-term purpose**: to embrace the long-term, sustainable ambitions of the Our Energy to evolve into a Pan-European open collaborative co-learning space for energy communities.

This long-term ambition is aligned with the Open Science and Citizen Science goals of the European Commission. Special attention is given to the following two Commission's aims for **Open Science policy under Horizon Europe**¹:

- **To promote the adoption of open science practices, from sharing research outputs as early and widely as possible, to citizen science**, and developing new indicators for evaluating research and rewarding researchers.
- **To engage and involve citizens, civil society organisations and end-users in co-design and co-creation processes** and promote responsible research and innovation.

2. Approach to developing this OER policy

2.1 Applying the strategic 7-phase framework

The author made use of the *Guidelines on the development of OER Policies* as a step-by-step guidebook on how to develop a systematic and effective policy on OER for the NEWCOMERS / Our Energy project, from conception to implementation. The Guidelines were used as a hands-on plan to acquire subject-matter knowledge, related to OER policies, as well as a framework to provoke critical thinking on how energy-related OER policy should be leveraged to address challenges in achieving the targets of both the SDG4 (Sustainable Development Goal 4 on quality education) and SDG7 (on affordable and clean energy). The figure below depicts the structure of the guidelines, that was

¹ More information here: https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/goals-research-and-innovation-policy/open-science_en.

followed by the author in all seven phases of chapter 3 of this assignment. At the end of each phase, a brief checklist is included that summarizes the **author's reflection on the usefulness/applicability of the specific phases from the Guidelines to this particular OER policy project.**

Figure 1: Map of the seven-phase policy process

2.2 Applying the Open Education Policy game

To analyse the gaps between the existing openness of the Our Energy platform and its future short-term and long-term vision, the author made use of the Open Education Policy game: <https://aberta.org.br/oe-game/>.

The author considered the game's key technical, pedagogical and legal-administrative statements from the Our Energy's OER policy aspect and then estimated the level of relevance of each statement for the policy project's future development. One statement from each of the open education aspect group (see Appendix for more) was chosen as the most important aspect and as a diagnostic tool for developing policy statements for the gap analysis and the masterplan, as referred to in the Guidelines. (The full results of the game can be seen in the Appendix.)

3. Our Energy's OER Policy - draft policy design through the 7 phases

3.1 Phase 1: OER potential for energy communities

In the first phase, we explain **why and how OER are a strategic opportunity to improve knowledge sharing, capacity building and universal access to quality co-learning inside and between the new clean energy communities.** We develop a sketch of the OER policy and define what expertise is required in the policy design process.

From the perspective of achieving the SDG4², the following two priority targets are identified:

- **Target 4.4:** relevant skills, including technical and vocational skills, for employment, decent jobs and entrepreneurship;
- **Target 4.7:** knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development.

² <https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal4>

As related to the Guidelines³ this emphasizes the need to focus on the following two educational challenges:

- To further **expand access to publicly funded non-formal and informal education inside and between energy communities** and in their relationships with other energy-sector stakeholders;
- To **provide quality open education, which develops creativity and knowledge** and ensures the acquisition of the foundational skills of literacy and numeracy, needed for successful operations of energy communities.

The major challenges the new clean energy communities are facing (from the OER perspective)⁴ are the following:

- Access to high-quality and accessible educational content for non-formal and informal learning that would allow **adaptation and contextualisation of content for specific local, regional or national purposes**. (In this way, OER could help foster the creative use of resources by experts and learners, where energy communities' representatives can be on both sides)
- Relevant, discoverable and affordable educational resources for Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) and skills development.

Therefore, the non-formal and informal learning environment and the capacities of energy communities (as experts and learners) will have to be supported through policy. Within this, the OER for energy communities can even become a **catalyst for general reforms and improvement in non-formal educational provision because they encourage social innovation around educational practices inside and between the new clean energy communities which themselves are important social innovations**.

Draft structure of this OER Policy⁵

Key enablers, relevant for this policy	Key focus areas	Targets to harness OER to achieve SDG4	Resource-related challenges (shortages of)
Public awareness about benefits of OE/OER for energy communities Partnership building and stakeholder engagement – taking a multidisciplinary approach	Policy on open licenses (for EU's research and other projects) OER repository for energy communities Quality assurance (multidisciplinary) Capacity building for energy communities Incentives for the creation and sharing of OER for the	OER for non-formal learning OER for TVET and skills development	Relevant, discoverable and affordable resources for TVET and skills development High-quality and accessible resources for non-formal and informal learning

³ Related to p. 7 in the *Guidelines on the development of open educational resources policies* (<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000371129>).

⁴ Related to p. 8 in the *Guidelines on the development of open educational resources policies* (<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000371129>).

⁵ Related to p. 9 (Figure 5) in the *Guidelines on the development of open educational resources policies* (<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000371129>).

Policy alignment (with EU's Open Science goals ⁶) Funding (part of Horizon Europe program)	experts/researchers community OER research and evidence		
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Open licensing

For this policy project, the open licensing aspect is of major importance, taking into account all five freedoms of OER as detailed by Wiley⁷.

Freedom of OER ⁸	Brief description of importance for the energy communities (ECs)
Retain	ECs can make, own and control copies of relevant educational materials which increases their access to resources
Revise	ECs can adapt, modify and alter existing content, e.g. add energy data relevant for their local context, translate it into their language etc.
Remix	ECs can combine original with other open content, e.g. take relevant energy-related information from 2 or more resources and remix them into a new resource, e.g. a presentation for a community meeting
Reuse	ECs can use original, revised or remixed copies of the publicly available educational resources
Redistribute	ECs can share copies of content, e.g. take a multimedia presentation from a joint repository and share it with their members and local policymakers

Open licensing of energy-related OER for energy communities can enable more efficient sharing of resources inside and between the energy communities and in their relationships with other key stakeholders in the energy sector and related sectors (e.g. climate, environment, transport, industry etc.). This will **improve the accessibility of high-quality learning materials and help build on the previous achievement of other research projects on energy communities** or related topics. In this way, a **virtuous circle of improvements can be co-created**. The CC BY-SA license will be suggested for all resources shared as part of the Our Energy platform. This license lets others remix, adapt, and build upon your work even for commercial purposes, as long as they credit you and license their new creations under identical terms. This is the license used by Wikipedia and is recommended for materials that would benefit from incorporating content from Wikipedia and similarly licensed projects.

⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/goals-research-and-innovation-policy/open-science_en

⁷ Related to p. 11 (Figure 6) in the *Guidelines on the development of open educational resources policies* (<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000371129>).

⁸ <https://www.opencontent.org/definition/>

Technical openness

This project aims to ensure that OER are easily accessible for all learners so that no special/advanced technical expertise (beyond basic technical/digital literacy skills) is needed from the energy communities' representatives to make use of the educational resources. These resources will be available in an open format, following open standards for development.

The process of OER adaptation, reuse and remix will be simplified by taking into consideration the ALMS rubric⁹ for technical openness:

A – Access to editing tools, such as those available through free and open-source software, without additional costs for energy communities and other users.

L – Level of expertise required to revise or remix, which needs to be increased with capacity-building programs. The project will aim to develop strong basic skills so that even the energy communities' members without advanced technical skills will be able to be part of the project.

M – Meaningfully editable resources, which enable the users to adapt and contextualise the educational resources according to their needs.

S – Source-file access, referring to OER as well as to the Learning Management System and other tools used, which allow users to adapt them to their specific needs.

Expertise needed

The following experts will be needed in the policy-design team to draft a successful and realistic policy for the project:

- **Expert for effective educational practices** (in charge of planning the use of context-appropriate digital learning tools)
- **Technical openness expert** (in charge of ensuring technical openness with the least possible complexity for the users)
- **A legal expert** in charge of the licensing aspect for resources of different origin, e.g. EU's research projects, universities, professional associations, education providers etc.)

Phase 1: Sketching the policy design – the checklist¹⁰

In the righthand column of the table below, the questions posed at the end of the chapter in the Guidelines are checked for their relevance to the case in hand.

Phase 1 – Guiding questions (summary description)	A / PA / NA (Applicable / Partly Applicable / Non Applicable)
Q 1: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- major challenges or issues and OER as a solution- expertise needed	A A

⁹ Related to p. 16 in the *Guidelines on the development of open educational resources policies* (<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000371129>).

¹⁰ Related to p. 17 in the *Guidelines on the development of open educational resources policies* (<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000371129>).

- who should be involved	PA – only description of expertise possible, no exact names of organisations or experts available yet
Q 2: - change of licensing regulations and practices, plans for reform - legal expertise needed	PA – general description of open licensing aims (CC BY-SA) A
Q 3: - ensuring technical openness, initial plans - technical expertise needed	A A

3.2 Phase 2: Our Energy's vision

Educational challenges

Our Energy's OER policy focuses on the following three points for action that are related to SDG 4 and the general educational challenges, and considers them in the context of the widespread use of OER¹¹:

- **Improving the relevance of learning content to individual energy communities' needs:** the goal is to enable experts and learners to collaborate when designing an up-to-date and adaptable learning content; it will be necessary to include capacity building for stakeholders involved but it should be up to them to decide how much they would like their capacities to be build-up, without limiting their rights/opportunities to be involved in the project more passively.
- **Providing multilingual and localized content,** which would enable high-quality learning content to be available in local/national languages of energy communities, adapted also from the content (i.e. energy-data) perspective.
- **Energy communities' skills development**¹² responding to the transformative changes in the energy sector (decentralisation of energy production, digitalisation, democratization etc., all influencing the role of energy communities) on one side and the future of learning¹³ (need for digital skills) on the other side.

All three challenges described above are significant and a clear way needs to be defined to contribute to facing them on the European level by making better, more efficient and more open use of the research and science exploring energy issues in general, and energy communities, in particular. The proposal will likely be welcomed not only by the energy experts and researchers but also by

¹¹ Related to p. 22 – 25 in the *Guidelines on the development of open educational resources policies* (<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000371129>) by selecting 3 out of 5 points of action considered.

¹² Collaboration with an existing project exploring the future EU energy sector skills set is important, i.e. the EDDIE project – a four-year (starting January 2020) Erasmus+ European Union funded collaborative project creating a Sector Skills Alliance (SSA). The Consortia is brings together 16 partners from 10 EU Countries. The challenge of the project is to develop a long-driven Blueprint for the digitalization of the European Energy sector to enable the matching between the current and future demand of skills necessary for the digitalization of the Energy sector. More information: <http://www.eddie-erasmus.eu/>

¹³ Personal reflection / feedback: the list of 'points of action' (see pages 23 – 25 in the Guidelines) is very similar but not identical to the list provided in the Guiding questions / Q1 on page 29. E.g. the 'skills development' point / goal is mentioned there (and not before on pages 23 – 25).

policymakers and decision-makers as it is in line with EU's Open Science and Citizen Science policy goals¹⁴.

Need for OER integration

The project aims at a *tight integration* of OER¹⁵ which would enable a new kind of co-learning within energy communities that was previously not available. It involves fully integrating OER into the complete energy communities' learning ecosystem. It is planned to be a catalyst for wider change in energy communities' educational and awareness-raising endeavours, and not only focused on providing new and open learning materials.

In line with the SAMR model¹⁶ (namely Substitution, Augmentation, Modification and Redefinition) the project aims at achieving the third level (Modification) but perhaps also the fourth level (Redefinition), where **OER are used as part of a whole to facilitate collaboration between energy experts to provide better materials, by encouraging collaboration between experts and learners and by increasing the relevance of the materials to the specifics of the energy-related context where learning takes place**. Modification and redefinition processes are likely to require significant efforts in the following two activity areas:

- **capacity-building** for both experts and learners,
- **new regulatory and administrative processes** (e.g. the requirements or incentives for publicly funded research projects to share their findings under an open license and to collaborate in the Our Energy's joint open educational efforts).

Formulating an input for a vision statement

In the **short term**, the NEWCOMERS project and the existing Our Energy platform will improve their outreach and openness for energy communities, fostering discussion and knowledge exchange between existing communities and other stakeholders, contributing to the achievement of the energy transition. In the **long term**, the outcomes of the NEWCOMERS project will have significantly contributed to creating an open, collaborative and sustainable digital space for co-learning within and between energy communities and other stakeholders.

¹⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/goals-research-and-innovation-policy/open-science_en

¹⁵ In relation to the alternative option – a *loose integration*, see p. 26 in the *Guidelines on the development of open educational resources policies* (<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000371129>).

¹⁶ More about the SAMR model: <https://www.schoology.com/blog/samr-model-practical-guide-edtech-integration>

Phase 2: Formulating a vision statement – the checklist¹⁷

In the righthand column of the table below, the questions posed at the end of the chapter in the Guidelines are checked for their relevance to the case in hand.

Phase 2 – Guiding questions (summary description)	A / PA / NA (Applicable / Partly Applicable / Non Applicable)
Q 1 ¹⁸ : Choose max. 3 from 5 goals & consequences for OER policy, explain and relate to specific challenges	A
Q 2: SAMR model and the role of OER policy	A
Q 3: A passage linking the future vision to current practices and make initial assertions about the short- and long-term expectations	A

3.3 Phase 3: Policy framing

Scope and scale

Scale: Scope:	Project / Pilot (in the 1st phase)	EU (when rolled-out)
Non-formal education and training	X	X
Technical and Vocational Education	X	X

This policy development is **project-based**, which means the policy starts on a small scale, based on the NEWCOMERS project and its Our Energy platform. This is an opportunity to gain an understanding of the inhibiting as well as about the supporting regulatory and behavioural factors that are to be taken into consideration in the 2nd phase when the **initiative is planned to go to scale on the EU institutional level**.

The policy will first be implemented in the scope of non-formal and informal education and training, provided by or to the energy communities, and will only at a later stage penetrate also on the scope of technical and vocational education. The scope of the 1st phase is in line with the research mission of the NEWCOMERS project that focuses on new clean energy communities, affecting (and limiting) the mandate of the NEWCOMERS consortium to non-formal and informal education.

Level of regulation vs. encouragement

As the NEWCOMERS project itself does not have a specific **OE(R)** focus but thematic research focus on exploring new clean energy communities, the creation of OER as part of the project will be encouraged through **regulating open licensing for the project's public outputs**. All key NEWCOMERS communications and dissemination materials, published on the Our Energy platform, are and will be licensed with a CC BY-SA license, and all consortium project partners will be encouraged to

¹⁷ Related to p. 28 and 29 in the *Guidelines on the development of open educational resources policies* (<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000371129>).

¹⁸ Personal reflection / feedback: Q1 (p. 29 in the Guidelines) at the end offers to add further issues related to your own context and society, which should be linked to the goals of SDG 4. Here and in general: it might be good to offer/mention to the reader/student the possibility to relate further issues more directly also to other SDGs beyond SDG 4. In my case, reference to the SDG 7 (Affordable and clean energy) could be made, where some of the targets are quite easily connectable also to the SDG 4 targets.

strengthen the message about the OER aspect in their research institutions¹⁹. Additionally, all NEWCOMERS partnering projects and organisations who share their research findings or knowledge on the Our Energy platform will be encouraged to openly license their work as well.

In this way, we will ensure that the **European research investments** (via Horizon2020, now the Horizon Europe and other financial programs) **have as broad a societal impact as possible** and encourage innovation in the development of new learning materials by openly licensing both new educational contents created with the support of European funding as well as the modifications made to existing educational content. Nevertheless, the 1st phase of the policy will focus on encouragement rather than regulation as it will focus on the deliverables of the NEWCOMERS and partnering projects, where the author and her team are in charge of the licensing aspect. In the 2nd phase, the policy is planned to be brought from the project level to the systemic EU level and bring in the mandatory perspective.

Policy alignment

This OER policy aligns with two broader EU's policy engagements, namely the:

- **EU's Open Science and Citizen science policy** with clear ambitions about their next steps under the Horizon Europe program²⁰,
- **Digital Education Action Plan 2021 – 2027**²¹ with its ambition to foster the development of a high-performing digital education ecosystem.

Phase 3: Defining the framework – the checklist²²

In the righthand column of the table below, the questions posed at the end of the chapter in the Guidelines are checked for their relevance to the case in hand.

Phase 3 – Guiding questions (summary description)	A / PA / NA (Applicable / Partly Applicable / Non Applicable)
Q 1: Define policy scope and scale	A
Q 2: Links between boxes in the policy framework	A
Q 3: Role of regulation vs. encouragement	A
Q 4: Alignment with other policies	A
Q 5: Review the policy vision	PA – no major changes/adjustments seem to be necessary at this point

¹⁹ There are 8 partners from 6 countries involved in the NEWCOMERS project. Six of them are research partners: Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam – The Netherlands, RWI – Germany, Oxford University – UK, CNR ITAE – Italy, University of Ljubljana – Slovenia; the industry partner is GEN-I – Slovenia and the communications partner is Consensus – Slovenia.

²⁰ See the eight ambitions of EU's Open Science and the planned next steps under the Horizon Europe here:

https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/research_and_innovation/knowledge_publications_tools_and_data/documents/ec_rtd_factsheet-open-science_2019.pdf

²¹ https://ec.europa.eu/education/education-in-the-eu/digital-education-action-plan_en

²² Related to p. 40 and 41 in the *Guidelines on the development of open educational resources policies* (<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000371129>).

3.4 Phase 4: Gap analysis

Awareness and knowledge of key stakeholders about OER and open licensing

The key stakeholders are the NEWCOMERS project:

- (1) **consortium members** (research and other partners) and
- (2) **other projects, organisations and individual experts** who partner with the NEWCOMERS project by sharing their research findings and knowledge on the Our Energy platform, and
- (3) the **energy communities as the project's primary beneficiaries**.

This OER policy needs to focus on informing and raising awareness of the importance of open licensing (for groups 1 and 2) and the user's benefits of OER (group 3). Data about the current situation on these issues is not available yet and the policy designers must plan how to obtain this data.

Availability and accessibility of high-quality content

This policy starts from the premise that **a lot of high-quality learning materials for energy communities are available from different energy research projects, but they are not open, not easily findable and are dispersed in different formats** on the specific project's websites. They lack a common, joint platform where they would be easily discoverable by the content topic they cover and available in formats that enable their easy reuse, remix, repurpose etc. And this is what the Our Energy platform with its OER policy offers for the existing learning materials. Concerning the new learning materials, the following two business models have to be considered:

- The **EU grants business model** (for learning materials, developed as part of the future Horizon Europe's and other research and innovation projects);
- The **community-based business models** where energy community members contribute to the production of learning materials (e.g. by their use, reuse, remix, repurpose etc. of existing learning materials).

A regulation framework to support the creation and use of OER

In general, the existing regulatory frameworks enable open licensing of learning materials (e.g. as part of the existing EU's Open Science policy) but **the awareness about the benefits of OER on the users' side needs to be increased**. Most of the learning materials from European projects are not technically open, so they are not easily adaptable (or not adaptable at all).

Additionally, quality assurance mechanisms and effectiveness evaluation of learning materials need to be introduced, and the learning materials need to be connected to the actual expected learning outcomes. The latter is most directly possible if all **learning takes place within a joint learning ecosystem**, comprising content, non-formal learning assessments and discussion forums.

ICT infrastructure to support access to and management of OER

ICT solutions (e.g. a Learning Management System) can comprehensively support both the discovery (through repositories) and adaptation (through easy editing). There are gaps in the available technical support and technical infrastructure that inhibit the adaptation of OER for new purposes and/or perhaps even restrict access for some potential learners.

The capacity of users to develop and use OER in the field

The training of experts (researchers and other experts) needs to be thoroughly planned as part of this policy's implementation. An enabling framework needs to be developed on the EU level to appropriately involve in these training the relevant researchers whose research work is funded by the EU. Collaboration between researchers from different projects and organisations needs to be encouraged to develop high-quality learning materials for energy communities. Additionally, the experts from the field need to be involved (e.g. energy community representatives) which might be challenging as the energy communities are very heterogeneous from their professionalization point of view.

Phase 4: Reviewing the results of the gap analysis – evaluation & checklist²³

In the righthand column of the table below, the questions posed at the end of the chapter in the Guidelines are checked for their relevance to the case in hand.

Phase 4 – Guiding questions (summary description)	Level of gap's relevance for this policy (1 – low, 5 – high)	A / PA / NA (Applicable / Partly Applicable / Non Applicable)	Connection to the OE Policy Game results²⁴ – the top 3 statements
Q 1: stakeholder's knowledge about open licensing and OER	4	PA – aware that we need this data but we do not have it yet	<u>Pedagogical aspect (part 1 - awareness):</u> »Our educational policies are designed with the participation of the community.«
Q 2: provision of high-level learning materials for all	3	A	
Q 3: learning materials provision's business models	4	A	
Q 4: OER enabling existing regulation	3	A	<u>Legal-administrative aspect:</u> »We have an open licensing policy, which means an OER policy.«
Q 5: need for quality assurance	4	A	
Q 6: need for ICT solutions	5	A	<u>Technical aspect:</u> »We have a digital repository for educational resources.«
Q 7: technical support/infrastructure	See Q 6	See Q 6	
Q 8: access to OER / technical support	See Q 6	See Q 6	
Q 9: experts' training and capacity building	5	A	<u>Pedagogical aspect (part 2 - skills):</u> »Our educational policies are designed with the participation of the community.«

²³ Related to p. 52 and 53 in the *Guidelines on the development of open educational resources policies* (<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000371129>).

²⁴ See Appendix for details of the Game play results.

Q 10: informal support structures	5	PA – aware that we need this data but we do not have it yet	
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3.5 Phase 5: Master plan

The following **six building blocks** are key to build this policy's masterplan:

Key building blocks	Objectives	Main activities and target sectors	Key partners for implementation	Indicators
Adopting an open licensing framework	To secure an open license for all learning materials, created or (re)used in the project	Analysis of existing licensing Encouragement of open licensing for all resources, used in the project	Resource developer (experts, researchers, energy communities) Legal and public tender experts (open licensing as a condition to get funding)	<u>Normative:</u> Explicit request for open licensing (CC 0, CC BY, CC BY-SA) of learning materials (to be eligible for funding under Horizon Europe, 2nd phase of the project) <u>Quantitative:</u> Share (%) of openly licensed materials (before and after the policy project)
Ensuring the development, storage and accessibility of OER	To make learning materials for energy communities easily discoverable, accessible and adaptable	Establishing a joint repository for energy-related OER (upgrade of the Our Energy platform) Adapt metadata to an appropriate open standard to facilitate discoverability.	Content developers IT / database / repository experts Metadata experts	<u>Normative:</u> OER are aligned to metadata which facilitates their discoverability <u>Quantitative:</u> Number of OER on the joint (Our Energy) platform Number of projects and organisations partnering with the Our Energy platform Number of languages used in OER
Aligning quality assurance procedures	To ensure appropriate quality assurance procedures for different types of learning materials	Develop an appropriate quality assurance that allows an external expert review as well as peer-review and a user-assessed procedure (this will not be an entry requirement for the OER)	Quality assurance experts Energy communities (as OER users) Energy experts (as OER developers)	<u>Normative:</u> The quality assurance policy adapted to the (expressed) specific needs of the users The joint repository allows users to rate (grade) OER <u>Quantitative:</u> Number of OER that pass the quality assurance review in the 1st round (vs. the 2nd round) + changes in time (how the quality of OER improves) The average grade of OER, given by users (and grade improvement through time)
Capacity building and awareness-raising	To ensure that all key stakeholders in the Our Energy ecosystem are knowledgeable about the benefits of OER	Stakeholder targeted capacity building on OER (webinars, online courses; training sessions, hands-on workshops; awareness-raising campaigns; network participation events for exchange and peer learning on OER)	Experts (content creators) Energy communities (creators in re/users of content)	<u>Normative:</u> Use of existing or adapted webinars and open courses available with targeted content for stakeholders with different levels of existing knowledge <u>Quantitative:</u> Share of stakeholders who successfully finish webinars, open courses and other available forms of capacity-building and training
Encouraging sustainable	To ensure that the policy implementation	Provide systemic EU-level funding for maintaining the Our	EU-level policymakers, the	<u>Normative:</u> Projects business plan that discusses the business

business models	and the energy-related OER creation and (re)use project are sustainable in the long term	Energy joint energy-related OER repository Provide project funding on EU-level (e.g. Horizon Europe) or at the national levels to develop and upgrade the Our Energy's features Encourage other financial sources (e.g. the energy business sector) to make use of the Our Energy + provide additional AI-supported customized services (freemium model)	European Commission Creators of national public tenders (national governments) Corporate energy sector – as either service subscribers or sponsors, donors	model(s), income and cost analysis, marketing plan; yearly evaluation of the business plan
Promoting evidence-based research on the impact of OER	Measure the real impact of the Our Energy project on the effectiveness of energy communities' operations	Launching of research activities and projects to evaluate the effectiveness of energy-related OER for energy communities Informing the policymakers and decision-makers about the results	Researchers Creators of public funding programmes (EU and national levels) Policymakers and decision-makers (EU and national levels)	<u>Normative:</u> Research studies and other research activities are launched in parallel with funding the Our Energy joint OER platform <u>Quantitative:</u> Number of research studies, other activities or projects investigating the impact of OER on energy communities learning practices Share of energy communities whose knowledge has improved through the use of OER Share of energy communities and other users who reuse, remix and repurpose materials from the Our Energy platform

Phase 5: Constructing the masterplan – the evaluation & checklist

(A - see table above for details; the N.A. building blocks are the following two: 'Ensuring the integration of OER at the level of curriculum development' and 'Setting up a governing body to implement OER policy', see chapter 3.6 for details about the latter.)

3.6 Phase 6: Governance and implementation plan

At this moment of our policy project development, only the first outlines of draft governance and implementation plan can be elaborated as key data still needs to be collected and the key stakeholders have to be engaged to further discuss the governance and implementation details of this policy, especially concerning budget and schedule, partner engagement, organizational structure and opportunities for international collaboration.

A mixed (top-down & bottom-up) method of policy implementation

It can be said already at this point that a mixed approach towards project implementation will be taken. The first phase of the project will take the **bottom-up approach**. In this phase, the NEWCOMERS, together with several partnering projects, will initiate open licensing of their energy-related educational resources for energy communities and strive to encourage this approach also

among related research projects. In the second phase, the focus will be on the **top-down approach**, when we plan to have several key stakeholders, including EU-level policymakers and decision-makers endorsing a new regulation, **supporting open licensing and other aspects of openness of educational materials funded as part of European energy-related research projects**. At that time, the Our Energy platform will be in place as an open collaborative digital space for education and awareness-raising inside and between energy communities.

Partner engagement strategy

A partner engagement strategy will be of crucial importance and the following key stakeholders will be engaged for consultation and advice as well as for supporting certain implementational tasks:

- **representatives of energy communities** (as the key user group of the project),
- **representatives of energy-related research and expert groups** (e.g. research and educational institutions, involved in research projects or providing energy education)
- **EU level policymakers and decision-makers**, involved in achieving the Energy Union's goals,
- **energy-sector stakeholders** (e.g. energy utilities, system operators, electricity distributors and traders etc.), whose core business is in/directly related to the effectiveness of the operations of energy communities.

The activities, messages and communication channels/tools for each partner will be defined at a later stage.

International collaboration via the UNESCO / OE4BW community

The broader international community of Open Education experts and practitioners will be informed about the project and activated to share experience and good practices from similar policy projects as part of the Open Education peer network. Namely, this policy will be further developed under the umbrella of the Open Education for a Better World (OE4BW) online mentoring program in 2021. More information on this in chapter 5.

Phase 6: Determining the implementation plan – evaluation & checklist²⁵

In the righthand column of the table below, the questions posed at the end of the chapter in the Guidelines are checked for their relevance to the case in hand.

Phase 6 – Guiding questions (summary description)	A / PA / NA (Applicable / Partly Applicable / Non Applicable)
Table: aligning the implementation strategy with the building blocks in the masterplan	NA – details about implementation method, budget activity & source, milestones and KPIs cannot be determined yet
Q 1: Enforcing mechanisms	PA – described only in very general terms
Q 2: Enabling mechanisms	PA - described only in very general terms
Q 3: Encouraging mechanisms	PA - described only in very general terms
Membership and responsibilities of the governing board and the coordinating body	NA – details for defining this are not available yet

²⁵ Related to p. 85 - 87 in the *Guidelines on the development of open educational resources policies* (<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000371129>).

Reassessing previous planning steps	PA – no major reconsiderations/adjustments of the masterplan or previous phases seem necessary at this point
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3.7 Phase 7: Policy launch

Communication strategy and target audience

Launching of this policy entails the organisation of several events on the EU and national levels, supported through high-level endorsements, **targeting different key stakeholders** with a central focus on the:

- **EU-level and national-level policymakers and decision-makers,**
- **Energy communities** and their umbrella associations on national levels and the EU level,
- **Energy experts and researchers.**

Details about activities, themes and events/channels of communication will be developed at a later stage, as input from these stakeholder groups will be collected already in earlier phases of the policy design process. In this way, relevant input for determining the possible endorsements will be collected and used. Additionally, the policy will be designed in an open way to allow feedback loops, which will enable constant review, monitoring and necessary adjustments of any of the activities in previous steps.

Phase 7: Launching the policy as an event and process – a checklist²⁶

In the righthand column of the table below, the questions posed at the end of the chapter in the Guidelines are checked for their relevance to the case in hand.

Phase 7 – Guiding questions (summary description)	A / PA / NA (Applicable / Partly Applicable / Non Applicable)
Q 1 – Communication strategy outline	PA - described only in very general terms
Q 2 – Reviewing and streamlining	PA - described only in very general terms
Q 3 – Full review of the policy impact	NA - details for defining this are not available yet

4. Challenges - topics for an open discussion

During the preparation of this assignment, the author has encountered several dilemmas that need further consideration and might be discussed at the oral presentation of the assignment:

Challenge 1: Mastering the project definition. Questions for discussion: How to appropriately define the project that is the subject of the policy design process? How to embrace the project's planned evolution from the policy design perspective? In my case, the ambition is to evolve from the project-based NEWCOMERS' Our Energy platform to the systemic, Pan-European open co-learning space for energy communities.

Challenge 2: From theory into practice – the road from 'assignment' to the 'real policy document'. Question for discussion: Which key steps will be taken to create, implement and evaluate the 'real' policy document for the Our Energy project? In which step to apply the OE Policy Game?

²⁶ Related to p. 97 in the *Guidelines on the development of open educational resources policies* (<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000371129>).

Challenge 3: Defining the co-creation principles. Questions for discussion: How to effectively plan the OE Policy Co-Creation Cycle?²⁷ If and how to make use of the OE Policy game (team play)?

5. Project's next steps: part of the OE4BW 200/21 mentoring programme

As mentioned in chapter 3.6, this policy project will be further developed under the OE4BW 2020/21 online mentoring program. Project title: Our Energy Open Education Policy. Developer: Mojca Drevenšek. Mentor: Vanessa Proudman, SPARC Europe. Please follow oe4bw.org for further information.

6. References

Atenas et al. (2020): Open Education Policies – Guidelines for co-creation. Open Education Policy Hub. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348009322_Open_Education_Policies_-_Guidelines_for_co-creation (retrieved 6th Feb 2021)

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Inamorato dos Santos, Andreia (2017): Going Open – Policy Recommendations on Open Education in Europe. European Commission. Going Open – Policy Recommendations on Open Education in Europe <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/eur-scientific-and-technical-research-reports/going-open-policy-recommendations-open-education-europe-openedu-policies> (retrieved 6th Feb 2021)

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Open Education Policy Game: <https://aberta.org.br/oe-game/> (retrieved 5th Feb 2021)

Appendix: Open Education Policy Game results (<https://aberta.org.br/oe-game/>)

Open Policy aspect group	Statement	Est. level of relevance for the project (1 – low, 3 – high)
TECHNICAL		
	We have a digital repository for educational resources.	3
	We have systems, tools and resources made with free software.	2
	Our suppliers can be replaced as we don't establish a technological lock-in contract with our software or hardware providers.	2
	The source code of our digital platforms belongs to our institution.	2
	Our users' personal data are protected and we never assign or share them with our platform or repository partners.	1
PEDAGOGICAL		

²⁷ See Atenas et al. (2020): Open Education Policies – Guidelines for co-creation, pages 26 – 35. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348009322_Open_Education_Policies_-_Guidelines_for_co-creation

	Our educational policies are designed with the participation of the community.	3
	Our students produce educational resources that are shared and available.	2
	Our teachers / civil servants produce educational resources that are shared and available.	2
	We encourage our teachers / civil servants to produce educational resources.	2
	We encourage collective and collaborative curatorship of our educational resources.	1
LEGAL-ADMINISTRATIVE		
	We have an open licensing policy, which means an OER policy.	3
	Agreements and contracts always include open licensing for various educational materials, including publications.	2
	We have a page disclosing terms of use in our digital platforms.	2
	We have a privacy policy page on our digital platforms.	2
	We use open licenses in our internal educational resources.	1